

MODERN CONDITIONS OF THE PREVALENCE OF STRONGYLOIDIASIS AMONG THE POPULATION: CLINICAL-EPIDEMIOLOGICAL, IMMUNO-PATHOGENETIC FEATURES, AND DIAGNOSTICS

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Abstract

Strongyloidiasis is a geohelminthiasis that primarily infects humans through the skin, particularly affecting the gastrointestinal system, and creates an immunosuppressive condition. After penetrating the skin, the larvae migrate to various organs. The clinical course of strongyloidiasis depends on the intensity of infection and the immune status of the organism, manifesting either symptomatically or asymptotically. Diagnosis is based on detecting strongyloid larvae in the intestinal contents and feces. Strongyloidiasis can survive in the human body for a long time and can cause several complications if left untreated. The main method of control is the timely detection and treatment of patients and improving environmental hygiene.

Keywords: strongyloidiasis, migration, prevalence, immunosuppression, control, treatment.

Introduction

Strongyloides stercoralis is a roundworm (nematode) that causes the disease strongyloidiasis. According to WHO data, over 600 million people worldwide are infected with this disease. Strongyloidiasis mainly affects the gastrointestinal system, triggers allergic processes during the migration phase, and can pose life-threatening risks in immunosuppressed individuals.

Humans are the main source of infection, with the primary route being through the skin. Occasionally, infection occurs through contaminated hands, vegetables, fruits, or water, as well as contact with contaminated soil. Larvae penetrate the intestinal wall and enter the bloodstream within one day [11] [p.22].

Between 2003 and 2013, more than 70% prevalence was observed in countries such as Peru, Kenya, and Guinea. High infection risk was recorded in 16 U.S. states. In Brazil, 13% of the population, in Thailand 23.7%, in Japan's Okinawa 5.2%, in China's agricultural regions 11.7%, and among Aboriginal communities in Australia, infection rates range from 35-60%. In North America and Europe, infection prevalence varies, mainly among migrants, refugees, and travelers. For instance, in Canada, 9-77% of Southeast Asian migrants and refugees were found to be infected, and in Spain, 17.2% of African migrants tested positive for strongyloidiasis [6] [p.42].

In subtropical regions (Lankaran-Astara and Sheki-Zagatala), infection rates range from 8.1% to 40.3%, while in arid subtropical regions, infection rates range from 1.6% to 7.6%. In Azerbaijan, information on the spread of this helminthiasis over the past 40 years is based on random screenings [2] [p.162-166].

According to WHO data from 2013, relatively few studies have been conducted on strongyloidiasis, and the incorrect selection of research and diagnostic methods prevents accurate assessment of its prevalence. Globally, the disease is primarily prevalent among approximately 370 million people living in tropical and subtropical regions with poor sanitation [4] [p.100-104].

Strongyloidiasis has both free-living and parasitic larvae. The permanent host of the parasite is humans, while cats and dogs serve as facultative hosts. Mature forms of the parasite inhabit the upper part of the small

intestine, the duodenum, the mucous membranes of the large intestine, the bile ducts, and the pancreatic ducts.

Strongyloidiasis has both male and female forms. Females lay up to 50 eggs 17 days after infection, from which larvae emerge. Therefore, in the feces and bile of such patients, rather than eggs, motile rhabditiform larvae are found. These larvae are excreted with feces, and under favorable environmental conditions (temperature and humidity), they become infectious filariform larvae within 1-5 days. After penetrating the skin, the larvae migrate to the lungs, from where they are swallowed and reach the intestines. It takes about one month for the larvae to reach sexual maturity.

Under unfavorable environmental conditions, free-living larvae transform into infectious larvae. These larvae enter the human body through the skin or mouth and reproduce. In some cases, rhabditiform larvae undergo direct or indirect development, with a third internal intestinal development stage also observed. In this process, rhabditiform larvae transform into filariform infectious larvae while still inside the intestines, without being excreted. These larvae penetrate the intestinal mucosa or exit through the anus and re-enter the bloodstream, leading to auto-infection. After a complex migration process, they settle in the small intestine, particularly in the duodenum, where they continue to parasitize.

Parasite localization usually occurs in the duodenum's Lieberkühn glands, but in cases of intense infection, mature helminths can also be found in the lower part of the small intestine, the transverse colon, bile ducts, and pancreatic ducts, causing severe changes in patients.

Filariform larvae migrate through the body via the blood and lymphatic systems, reaching the liver, heart, and lungs. From the respiratory tract, they are swallowed and enter the gastrointestinal system, where the male and female forms of the parasite emerge. Males die in the intestinal cavity, while females penetrate the intestinal mucosa and continue to develop there.

Infectious larvae penetrate the skin of people walking barefoot on the ground, which manifests as "ground itch." Swallowed larvae migrate to the lungs, where they mature, and are then swallowed again when the infected person coughs [13].

Thus, infectious larvae develop both in the soil and in the host's intestines. These larvae penetrate the intestinal mucosa or skin, starting the infection cycle anew, leading to a chronic form of the disease. At the site where infectious larvae penetrate the skin, rashes may appear. Coughing, itching, eosinophilia, leukocytosis, and increased ESR levels appear 7-10 days after infection, followed by diarrhea and abdominal pain. Larvae begin to be excreted with feces 3-4 weeks after infection [14].

Clinical course: acute, chronic, hyperinfection forms.

- **Acute form:** During the spread of strongyloidiasis in the lungs, symptoms such as coughing, shortness of breath, and bronchospasm are observed. X-rays show opacity in the chest and infiltrates or abscesses in the lungs. Diarrhea is less common during the gastrointestinal phase.

- **Chronic form:** Symptoms include shortness of breath, wheezing, diarrhea, abdominal pain, constipation, vomiting, weight loss, pneumonia, lung hemorrhage, arthritis, nephrotic syndrome, and liver damage.

- **Hyperinfection form:** X-rays of the lungs reveal bilateral infiltrates, respiratory failure, frequent abdominal pain, nausea, and gastrointestinal symptoms such as vomiting. The mortality rate for this form ranges from 85-100% [10] [p.691-698].

The clinical progression is divided into two stages: the migration and intestinal stages. In the migration stage, patients may experience chills, fatigue, fever, cough (sometimes with sputum), and various skin rashes, particularly rubella-like rashes. There have been instances where, during the migration stage, larvae pass from the mother to the fetus in pregnant women. In the intestinal stage, the patient may experience abdominal pain, bloating, excessive salivation, nausea, vomiting, and diarrhea (which may be mucous or sometimes bloody) [1] [p.22].

Strongyloidiasis can persist in the human body for a long time and can cause various complications if left untreated. Auto-infection leads to continuous invasion in immunocompromised individuals, and in immunosuppressed conditions, the infection can become more severe, followed by the development of hyperinfection. The clinical course of strongyloidiasis depends on the intensity of the infection and the immune status of the body, and it can present in either manifest or chronic asymptomatic forms [7] [p.664-670].

Diagnosis Strongyloidiasis diagnosis is based on detecting the parasite in feces, duodenal contents, and tissue samples. Diagnostic methods include stool microscopy, concentration techniques, culture methods, direct parasite detection techniques such as polymerase chain reaction (PCR), and biopsy [9] [p.7-20]. Diagnosis of strongyloidiasis is based on finding strongyloid larvae in the intestinal contents and feces. The Berman method is commonly used, and this method is based on the principle of the larvae's movement towards heat. Other diagnostic tests include:

1. **Duodenal examination:** This test examines the duodenal contents (all 3 portions of duodenal juice).
2. **Sputum examination:** Sputum is examined to study the contents of the lungs and respiratory tract.

3. **Stool examination:** The Berman method is mainly used to detect larvae in the feces, and this method is considered the gold standard for diagnosing strongyloidiasis [15].

Procedure for examination:

1. 10-15 ml of warm water (40°C) is added to the stool sample brought to the laboratory;

2. After 20-30 minutes, the solution is transferred into a test tube;

3. It is left to settle for 10-15 minutes or centrifuged at 1500 revolutions per minute;

4. The sediment is then examined under a microscope, and motile, weakly motile, or immobile larvae are detected. Immobile larvae are examined under high magnification. It is reported that larvae can remain alive for 1-1.5 days when feces are stored at 6°C in a refrigerator. The larvae become active after exposure to warm water, and dead larvae do not undergo morphological changes. The effectiveness of the Berman method is as high as 96%, while the ordinary smear method is only 4.5% effective. In the U.S., the mortality rate among immunocompromised patients with severe strongyloidiasis is 69% [8] [p.141-148].

A blood test for antigens can help detect antigens and is used when parasitic infections are suspected but not detected by other methods. A critical problem in diagnosing strongyloidiasis in immunocompromised patients is the non-specific nature of symptoms until the disease reaches its full development. Recovery from complicated strongyloidiasis in immunosuppressed patients, especially those with secondary bacterial and fungal infections, shows poor results.

Treatment. Treatment of strongyloidiasis involves the use of albendazole, mebendazole, ivermectin, and levamisole. After mass treatment with ivermectin, seropositivity decreases from 21% to 5%. Treatment is repeated after 10 days. After treatment, both clinical and laboratory evaluations should be carried out. Laboratory evaluations include stool examination, general blood tests, and serological examinations. In severe forms of strongyloidiasis, stool examination should be conducted for at least two weeks. Eosinophilia typically normalizes within one month, while serological indicators return to normal within 6-12 months. Therefore, consecutive tests every 3-6 months for two years are recommended.

Despite the widespread prevalence of strongyloidiasis, significant shortcomings exist in current control programs, particularly in diagnostic methods. Although several diagnostic methods exist, the absence of the Berman method, especially in endemic areas, prevents the complete detection of the disease. The increase in the spread of *S. stercoralis* among the population is associated with poor personal hygiene, inadequate water sources in endemic areas, and the development of tourism. Therefore, there is an urgent need to improve the diagnosis of strongyloidiasis [5] [p. 20-25].

Control Measures. The fight against strongyloidiasis involves timely detection of cases, treatment until full recovery, and environmental sanitation. Strongyloidiasis patients often present to medical institutions with mixed symptoms. In such cases, strongyloidiasis is often misdiagnosed as other diseases (e.g., dysentery, gastritis, colitis, hepatobiliary diseases, duodenal ulcer,

appendicitis), which leads to ineffective treatment. To avoid such errors and to detect strongyloidiasis patients on time, patients with gastrointestinal, biliary tract, gallbladder, and liver diseases, skin rashes (especially rubella-like), as well as those with high eosinophil levels in their blood, should be screened for strongyloidiasis. Detected patients should be treated both specifically and pathogenetically in either a hospital or outpatient setting until fully cured. Another measure in the fight against strongyloidiasis is ensuring environmental cleanliness. Every household area should be kept clean, and waste and garbage should be regularly disposed of [12].

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